

Therapeutic and cosmetic potential of Rosaceae oils: comparative analysis of Japanese quince seed oil, rosehip oil, and apricot kernel oil

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Abstract

Vegetable oils emerge as a valuable constituent in both cosmetic and pharmaceutical formulations due to their beneficial properties upon topical application and their natural origin. Plant-derived oils exhibit well-pronounced antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and skin-regenerating properties, which are strongly influenced by their composition. The current review discusses, in a comparative context, the composition, physicochemical characteristics, and formulation applicability of three oils from the Rosaceae family: rosehip oil, Japanese quince oil, and apricot kernel oil. A summary of their applications in cosmetic formulations is provided, and the research progress regarding their therapeutic potential is updated, highlighting the latest results in the field.

Keywords

anti-age effect, natural oil, phytosterols, skin hydration, unsaturated fatty acids, vitamin E

Introduction

In recent years, natural-based ingredients have attracted significant research and commercial attention due to their dual role as active agents and sustainable excipients in the cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries. Their inclusion in cosmetic formulations is a current trend in the sector, driven by consumers' preferences for both effective and environmentally friendly products (Ferreira et al. 2021). Of particular interest are vegetable oils due to their numerous advantages, such as emollient, antioxidant, and photoprotective properties, as well as good skin compatibility and a tolerability profile (Abdalla et al. 2024). In the

field of pharmaceuticals, plant-derived oils are highly evaluated for their anti-inflammatory and wound/scar-healing effects and barrier-repairing properties in conditions such as dermatitis, eczema, or xerosis (Lin et al. 2017). The aforementioned positive qualities are mainly attributed to their composition, in particular the level of unsaturated fatty acids, tocopherols, phytosterols, carotenoids, and polyphenols, which together in a complementary manner provide optimal skin hydration and barrier function, reduce oxidative stress to a minimum, and facilitate epithelialization (Budzianowska et al. 2025). Their beneficial effects as natural excipients include enhanced skin permeability, improved bioavailability, formulation stabilization,

and serving as structural constituents in the composition of nanoscale carriers.

The Rosaceae family includes dicotyledonous, flowering plants of the order Rosales with approximately 4,828 known species in 91 genera. It is an important botanical source of trees, shrubs, subshrubs, and herbaceous plants, distributed worldwide, primarily in the temperate zone of the Northern Hemisphere (Xu and Deng 2017). Some of its representatives with well-established roles in cosmetic products include *Prunus dulcis* (source of almond oil), *Rosa damascena* (source of rose essential oil), and *Rosa canina* (source of rosehip oil). Others, such as *Chaenomeles japonica* and *Prunus armeniaca*, and their derived oils, are emerging as high-value cosmetic and pharmaceutical ingredients.

Japanese quince seed oil is extracted from the seeds of *C. japonica* and is characterized by a high content of linoleic acid (50–55%), tocopherols, and phytosterols, which impart barrier-repair and anti-inflammatory effects (Ben-Othman et al. 2023). The polyunsaturated fatty acid content, in addition to the present polyphenols, indicates antioxidant and epithelial-regenerating properties. Rosehip oil is obtained from the *Rosa canina* seeds and is rich in α -linolenic acid (25–35%), carotenoids, and phenolic compounds. It is well recognized for its wound-healing properties, regenerative effects on photoaged skin, and scar-minimizing effects (Oargă et al. 2024). Apricot kernel oil is derived from *Prunus armeniaca* and is predominantly composed of oleic acid (60–70%). It is best known for its emollient, skin-soothing properties and oxidative stability, which contribute to its inclusion in various types of formulations (Makrygiannis et al. 2023).

Despite their promising properties, the selected oils differ substantially in chemical composition, oxidative stability, and sensory profile, which affects their formulation applicability. Furthermore, although individual studies have documented the composition and biological effects of these three oils, a comparative evaluation of their therapeutic and cosmetic potential remains lacking. In this regard, the present review aims to provide a comprehensive description of the chemical composition, biological activities, and formulation opportunities of Japanese quince seed oil, rosehip oil, and apricot kernel oil. In addition to their established use in skin and hair care, particular emphasis is placed on their therapeutic applications in dermatology, including their wound-healing, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial activities.

Rosehip seed oil (*Rosa canina* seed oil)

Rosehip seed oil has a rich history as a therapeutic agent and a popular beauty product. It contains a high percentage of unsaturated fatty acids, the qualitative and quantitative composition of which may differ among individual oils due to genetic factors, growing conditions (e.g., soil properties and environmental factors such as temperature, light, rainfall, and altitude), harvest time, and the extraction methods applied. A comparative analysis of the physicochemical characteristics of rosehip oil, Japanese quince oil, and apricot kernel oil is provided in Table 1.

Among the polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) in rosehip oil, the highest concentrations are of linoleic acid (36–55%) (Ilyasoğlu 2014; Mannozi et al. 2020), α -linolenic acid (15–27%) (Mannozi et al. 2020; Wirkowska-Wojdyła et al. 2024), and oleic acid (15–22%) (Ilyasoğlu 2014; Mannozi et al. 2020).

Linoleic acid (C18:2, ω -6) and α -linolenic acid (C18:3, ω -3) have beneficial effects in the treatment of various skin diseases, such as atopic dermatitis, psoriasis, acne vulgaris, and systemic lupus erythematosus. They contribute to skin barrier function, maturation, and differentiation of the *stratum corneum* (SC), raise the threshold of sunburn, and inhibit pro-inflammatory cytokines such as tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), interferon- γ (IFN- γ), and interleukin-12 (IL-12) (McCusker and Grant-Kels 2010). Oleic acid (ω -9) is an excellent emollient agent commonly used in creams, lotions, and serums to improve skin hydration and texture. It is a well-known penetration enhancer that can help reduce the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles. In hair care, it prevents hair dryness and is reported to improve texture and shine (Stryjecka et al. 2025). The fatty acids in vegetable oils, along with ceramides and cholesterol, help the skin function as an effective protective barrier, maintaining the balance between the body's internal and external environments and protecting against exogenous factors and substances, including bacterial infections (Wertz 2018). Symptoms of polyunsaturated fatty acid deficiency include dry skin, slow wound healing, inflammation, increased sensitivity to irritation, and excessive epidermal exfoliation, particularly in conditions such as psoriasis or atopic dermatitis (Jara et al. 2020).

In addition to PUFAs, rosehip oil also contains saturated fatty acids such as palmitic and stearic acids. Palmitic acid (C16) has an emollient effect, moisturizing and

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of rosehip, Japanese quince, and apricot kernel oils (<https://www.nhrorganicoils.com>, <https://www.avenalab.com>, Özcan 2010; Ayas and Demirel 2012; Gornas et al. 2013; Eren et al. 2023).

Property	Rosehip seed oil (origin: Bulgaria)	Japanese quince seed oil (origin: Latvia)	Apricot kernel oil (origin: Turkey)
Color	Yellow to dark orange	Pale yellow to light gold	Light yellow to yellow
Specific gravity (at 20 °C)	0.830–0.990	0.920	0.910–0.930
Refractive index (at 20 °C)	1.360–1.490	~1.4738 (20 °C)	1.460–1.475
Peroxide value (mEq O ₂ /kg)	2.04	0.60	≤ 5.0
Free fatty acid (%)	< 7.0	No records	0.279–0.700
Acid value (mg KOH/g)	1.5	0.88 to 2.5	0.39–2.06

softening the skin, restoring its natural barrier function, and providing a smooth, hydrated complexion. These effects may be related to its natural similarity to epidermal lipids, while its ability to reduce interfacial surface tension determines its role as a surfactant (Mieremet et al. 2019; Nicolaou and Kendall 2024). In decorative cosmetics, palmitic acid contributes to smooth application and even distribution of pigments, ensuring flawless coverage (de Clermont-Gallerande 2020). Stearic acid (C18) is an emollient, emulsifier, and thickening agent used in the production of cosmetic formulations in concentrations of 2–5% for creams and lotions and 25% for solid cosmetic products. It provides a gentle cleansing effect without removing the skin lipids (Mukherjee et al. 2010).

Another important constituent includes antioxidants such as tocopherols and provitamin A (β -carotene), phytosterols, and phenolic acids. Tocopherols are essential compounds of the unsaponifiable fraction and are present as liposoluble phenols in vegetable oils (Mannozi et al. 2020). They are antioxidants and sources of vitamin E, which is abundant in rosehip oil. It accumulates in cell membranes, thereby protecting lipid components from oxidative damage and improving the function of the skin barrier. The protective actions of vitamin E are also evident in its ability to reduce UV-induced DNA damage, which is crucial for preventing long-term deterioration of dermal tissue and promoting skin health (Elbouzidi et al. 2025). Beta-carotene is one of the predominant carotenoids in rosehip oil (reaching up to 77% of the total carotenoid content), contributing toward collagen production by upregulating transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β) and simultaneously inhibiting its degradation via the suppression of matrix metalloprotease (MMP) activity (Bibi et al. 2025; Stanescu et al. 2025).

Phytosterols are well-tolerated, biologically active compounds often included in cosmetic formulations for sensitive, irritated, or dry skin and scalp (Górnaś and Rudzińska

2016). They exert moisturizing properties by maintaining a hydrolipidic film on the epidermal surface and limiting transepidermal water loss (TEWL) (Xinyue 2024). When applied topically, they can stimulate fibroblast growth factor activity, thereby restoring skin integrity, inhibit pro-inflammatory mediators, and modulate the immune response (Chang et al. 2023; Shen et al. 2024). Phytosterols exhibit a pronounced anti-aging effect by inhibiting enzymes such as collagenase (MMP-1) and stimulating new collagen production, improving skin firmness and elasticity (Tanaka et al. 2015). The primary phytosterol present in rosehip oil is β -sitosterol, which accounts for approximately 83% of the total content (Ilyasoğlu 2014).

Phenolic acids exhibit potent antioxidant activity by limiting the formation of free radicals and protecting skin cells from oxidative damage, which leads to the breakdown of DNA, lipid membranes, and structural proteins. They can improve skin elasticity and overall health, helping prevent skin dehydration, wrinkles, and discoloration. Some of the most abundant phenolic acids in the composition of rosehip oil include ferulic, caffeic, and cinnamic acids. Ferulic acid has been widely used in sunscreens, as it can absorb UV radiation, stimulate collagen synthesis, and exert anti-inflammatory effects. It is often found in anti-wrinkle creams and products for the treatment of seborrheic dermatitis and acne. Caffeic acid exhibits anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties, making it suitable for use in products treating folliculitis, acne, and rosacea. Cinnamic acid is used in cosmetics for its aromatic properties, UV protection, and antioxidant effects, which are attributed to its ability to mitigate oxidative stress (Elbouzidi et al. 2025).

Therapeutic and cosmetic application of rosehip oil

Rosehip oil has well-established use in various cosmetic products, as shown in Table 2. An emerging trend is its use

Table 2. Cosmetic products containing rosehip seed oil.

Cosmetic product	Main “green ingredients”	Type of product	Product claims	Reference
Ultra Hydrating Face Cream	Aloe vera; manuka honey; sweet almond oil; rosehip seed oil	Face cream	Hydrating and nourishing properties; moisture barrier recovery	https://www.trilogyproducts.co.uk
Rosehip Transformation Cleansing Oil	Rosehip oil; sweet almond oil; grapeseed oil; papaya seed oil	Facial cleanser	Gently removes makeup and impurities; leaves skin soft and radiant	https://www.trilogyproducts.co.uk
Organic Rosehip Oil Antioxidant+	Rosehip oil; tomato seed oil; acai fruit oil	Facial oil	Powerful antioxidant protection; improves skin tone and texture; reduces signs of aging	https://www.trilogyproducts.co.uk
Rosehip BioRegenerate Oil	Rosehip seed oil (CO ₂ extract); rosehip fruit oil	Facial oil/serum	Improves skin firmness and elasticity; minimizes the appearance of scars and fine lines	https://www.paiskincare.ie/
1000 Roses Soothing Body Lotion	Plant stem cells (Alpine rose and bioactive berry complex); rose flower distillate; shea butter; argan kernel oil; rosehip seed oil	Body lotion	Hydrating, nourishing, and moisturizing properties	https://andalou.com
Wild Rose Shampoo	Rosehip seed oil; rosemary leaf extract; nettle leaf extract; matricaria flower extract	Shampoo	Nourishing effect	https://www.faithinnature.co.uk
Rosehip Dry Body Oil	Rosehip oil; coconut oil; grapeseed oil; jojoba oil; sweet almond oil	Body oil	Deep nourishment; improves skin elasticity	https://www.frankbody.com

in hair care products, as topical administration has been shown to accelerate the transition from the telogen to the anagen phase in hair follicles, support their development, and increase hair growth (Stryjecka et al. 2025).

The therapeutic effect of rosehip oil on the skin has been the subject of numerous studies. Pronounced wound-healing activity of rosehip oil was reported, which may be attributed to the induction of macrophage transition into the anti-inflammatory M2 type, leading to a reduction in inflammatory responses (Lei et al. 2019). The wound-healing effect of rosehip oil was investigated in a comparative study with olive oil, as conducted by Aydin et al. (2025). The *in vitro* scratch assay and *in vivo* studies on excisional wounds revealed increased wound closure when rosehip oil was applied. Additionally, increased expression of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β) was observed, suggesting enhanced epithelial tissue regeneration (Aydin et al. 2025). A clinical trial involving 108 patients with postsurgical scars showed that applying rosehip oil twice daily for 12 weeks significantly improved erythema, discoloration, and wound atrophy compared with the untreated control group (Valerón-Almazán et al. 2015).

The anti-inflammatory effect of rosehip oil was studied by Dewedar et al. (2025), who investigated its efficacy in an *in vivo* study on rats with induced mucosal ulcer. The results showed that rosehip oil emulsion successfully stimulated the proliferation of human gingival fibroblasts, increased epithelial thickness, and diminished the inflammatory response (Dewedar et al. 2025). The anti-inflammatory activity of rosehip oil can be further explored in the treatment of various skin disorders, such as eczema or neurodermatitis.

Rosehip oil was also successfully formulated in nanoscale carriers. Sağıroğlu (2024) prepared nanostructured lipid carriers with suitable physicochemical characteristics (size of 180 nm, polydispersity index <0.3) and superior permeation and retention in the SC and viable epidermis layers compared with plain rosehip oil. Encapsulated in nanocapsules, rosehip oil has been reported to exhibit improved oxidation resistance against UV-induced oxidation. The elaborated nanocapsules were further incorporated into chitosan gel, exhibiting suitable rheological characteristics and excellent physical stability (Contri et al. 2015).

Of interest is also the study by Hashimoto et al. (2025), which develops rosehip oil nanoparticles and evaluates their efficacy in a psoriasis-induced mouse model. The obtained nanocarriers exhibit a small size (100 nm), facilitating their uptake by human keratinocytes (HaCaT cells) and enabling them to suppress keratinocyte proliferation and inhibit the release of inflammatory cytokines. The *in vivo* studies showed that intradermal application of rosehip oil nanoparticles improved psoriasis-related lesions in mice and reduced reactive oxygen species levels (Hashimoto et al. 2025).

Japanese quince seed oil (*Chaenomeles japonica* seed oil)

The seeds of *Chaenomeles japonica* (Japanese quince) make up to 9% of the weight of fresh fruit and are used to produce oils rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids and lipophilic bioactive compounds such as tocopherols, phyosterols, and carotenoids (Ben-Othman et al. 2023). A literature reference indicates that the absorption spectrum of Japanese quince seed oil spans 400 to 440 nm, suggesting the presence of a high concentration of carotenoids responsible for the oil's yellow color.

Regarding its metabolic composition, nineteen fatty acids have been identified in Japanese quince oil, with the highest content found for linoleic acid (C18:2) at 52.4%, oleic acid (C18:1) at 33.8%, and palmitic acid (C16:0) at 9.5%, representing 95.7% of the total fatty acids. The fatty acids in Japanese quince oil are incorporated into cell membranes, which help regenerate the damaged lipid barrier of the epidermis and limit TEWL. When applied to the skin, they can maintain a pH between 4.0 and 6.5 and accelerate wound healing (Yang et al. 2020).

Among the tocopherols in Japanese quince oil, α -, β -, γ -, and δ -tocopherols are present. They protect against both lipid peroxidation and collagen cross-linking and stabilize cell membranes by inhibiting the oxidation of arachidonic acid to phospholipids. In contrast to *Rosa canina* oil, Japanese quince seed oil exhibits a low amount of phyosterols, with the highest content being β -sitosterol (6.31%) (Górnaś et al. 2013). Six phenolic compounds have been identified in Japanese quince seed oil: 4-hydrobenzoic acid, vanillic acid, vanillin, *p*-coumaric acid, and ferulic acid (Górnaś et al. 2013). Similar to rosehip oil, Japanese quince seed oil can inhibit photoaging, promote regeneration, and absorb UVB and UVA radiation. A negligible amount of chlorophyll (0.11 mg/kg) is found in Japanese quince seed oil. As an active ingredient, it possesses anti-aging properties and has the potential to treat acne and minimize the appearance of enlarged pores. Additionally, chlorophyll facilitates wound healing in incision wounds, prevents infections, and neutralizes unpleasant odors (Berry 2018).

Squalene is also present in the oil in low amounts (0.67 mg/g). It is quickly absorbed and is characterized by high spreadability and a non-greasy texture. Squalene can accelerate cell growth, help the skin obtain essential nutrients, and create a barrier against moisture loss (Du et al. 2024). In pharmaceutical products, squalene exhibits promising potential in the treatment of conditions such as eczema, allergies, and psoriasis (Senbagalakshmi et al. 2019). Additionally, it has been reported to possess antioxidant properties that help prevent lipid peroxidation of the skin's surface (Huang et al. 2009).

The characteristic yellow color of Japanese quince seed oil may be attributed to the β -carotene it contains, with

a reported concentration of 10.69 mg/kg (Górnaś et al. 2013). It has strong antioxidant potential, effectively neutralizing the singlet form of oxygen. β -carotene penetrates well into the SC and, to some extent, accumulates in the cell membranes of corneocytes. In the epidermis, it is converted to retinol and its esters and is characterized by excellent skin tolerability. These properties qualify this compound as a particularly valuable active ingredient in the fight against aging and in skin protection. Additionally, its coloring effect determines its use in decorative cosmetics as a pigment (Arct and Mieloch 2016).

Therapeutic and cosmetic application of Japanese quince seed oil

Among the discussed oils, Japanese quince seed oil is included in the fewest cosmetic products (Table 3), and its therapeutic potential has not yet been fully investigated. Data from the literature report only the beneficial effects of *Cydonia oblonga* (ethanolic extract and mucilage) in alleviating symptoms of atopic dermatitis (Kawahara et al. 2017) and promoting skin proliferation (Mammadov et al. 2024). To address the research gap, our previous work focused on the development of cosmetic creams containing Japanese quince oil, rosehip oil, and apricot kernel oil solely and in combination, as well as evaluating their antioxidant activity. The cream based on Japanese quince oil exhibited the highest antioxidant activity evaluated by the FRAP method among the tested formulations (Hutova et al. 2025), which further supports the potential of this oil as a valuable cosmetic and pharmaceutical ingredient.

Apricot kernel oil (*Prunus armeniaca* kernel oil)

The nuts of *Prunus armeniaca* are the primary source of apricot kernel oil, in which it is present in amounts of up to 50% (González-García and García 2022). Apricot kernel oil derived via the cold-pressing technique consists of 92–98% lipids as the main component, in addition to phytosterols, α -sitosterols, and tocopherols as a minor fraction (Bhanger et al. 2020).

A total of ten fatty acids have been found in apricot kernel oil, among which are palmitic, palmitoleic, margaric, stearic, cis-vaccenic, oleic, linoleic, α -linolenic, arachidic,

and gondoic acids. The highest amount is oleic acid (70–76%) (Kaya et al. 2008), followed by linoleic acid (17–23%) (Saçkesen et al. 2025). Comparative studies conducted on sweet and bitter apricot kernels revealed that sweet kernel oil is richer in oleic acid than bitter kernel oil, while bitter kernels contain higher levels of linoleic and palmitic acids. Additionally, the presence of the nut shell has been reported to increase linoleic acid concentration and decrease the concentration of oleic acid (González-García et al. 2022). Besides its high fatty acid content, apricot kernel oil also contains small amounts of high-value compounds, including tocotrienols, phytosterols, carotenoids, and phenolic compounds. Among the tocochromanols, the most abundant is γ -tocopherol (approximately 91–94%), which exhibits anti-inflammatory properties by suppressing pro-inflammatory mediators such as prostaglandin E2 and cyclooxygenase-derived metabolites. This activity may contribute to the soothing and protective action of apricot kernel oil when applied topically, especially in formulations intended for damaged or irritated skin.

Regarding the phytosterol content, nine types of phytosterols were identified (β -sitosterol, campesterol, Δ 5-avenasterol, Δ 7-stigmasterol, gramisterol, cholesterol, 24-methylene-cycloartanol, Δ 7-avenasterol, and citrostadienol) (Bai et al. 2021), with qualitative ratios varying depending on external or cultivation-related factors. A higher amount of squalene (compared with Japanese quince oil) is present in apricot kernel oil, ranging from 12.6 to 43.9 mg/100 g of oil depending on the apricot variety (González-García et al. 2020).

Apricot kernel oil also contains carotenoids, minerals (Ca, Cu, Fe, Mg, Mn, Na, and P), vitamins (A, B1, B2, B6, B17, and E), and phytoestrogens (beta-estradiol), as well as the characteristic cyanogenic glycoside amygdalin (Saçkesen et al. 2025). Lutein, zeaxanthin, beta-cryptoxanthin, and beta-carotene are the main carotenoids in apricot kernel oil, while neoxanthin, antheraxanthin, and violaxanthin each represent less than 10% of the total (González-García et al. 2020). Beta-estradiol is known to increase the production of extracellular matrix proteins and enhance collagen production, making it a valuable component in anti-aging creams (Bhanger et al. 2020). Amygdalin, on the other hand, possesses anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties and can alleviate psoriasis lesions and improve skin barrier damage (Wang et al. 2024).

Table 3. Cosmetic products containing Japanese quince oil/extract.

Cosmetic product	Main “green ingredients”	Type of product	Product claims	Reference
Kuni Japanese Quince Natural Hydrating Lotion	Japanese quince (extract and oil); alfalfa extract; yarrow herb extract	Lotion (face/body/hands)	Hydrating and antioxidant properties; improves skin texture and revitalizes skin	https://int.japanesetaste.com
The Juice Moisturizing Power Fluid	Quince juice; stevia; linseed; alfalfa; sesame seed oil; spelt, jojoba, and avocado oils; vitamin E; hyaluronic acid	Mastic tree resin extract; shiitake; Japanese quince seed oil; cold-pressed hemp seed oil	Strengthens the skin’s protective barrier; balances sebum secretion; smooths fine lines; brightens skin tone; protects the skin from cell damage caused by UV radiation and external stressors	https://djusie.com

Characteristic of apricot kernel oil is its ability to inhibit the formation of bacterial biofilms due to its constituents' ability to disrupt the bacterial communication system (Joujou et al. 2024). In a comparative study evaluating the antibacterial activity of four natural oils (apricot, date, grape, and black seed), apricot kernel oil showed the highest antimicrobial activity against *Proteus mirabilis* (Joujou et al. 2024).

Therapeutic and cosmetic application of apricot kernel oil

Apricot kernel oil has been widely used in various types of cosmetic products (Table 4). When topically applied, it is

E. coli, while the most potent antifungal activity was demonstrated against *A. flavus* and *M.ucedo*. Additionally, antileishmanial activity (against *L. major*) was also noted. The results obtained support the feasibility of using apricot kernel oil as an antimicrobial agent in cosmetic or pharmaceutical formulations (Hamid et al. 2024).

Of particular interest is the study conducted by Hong et al. (2024), which evaluated the impact of apricot kernel oil extract on cognitive function and inflammatory factors in a rat model of hemorrhagic shock. The authors reported neuroprotective effects at a dose of 400 mg/kg, characterized by preserved neuron density and reduced cerebral hemorrhage volume (Hong et al. 2024).

Table 4. Cosmetic products containing apricot kernel oil.

Cosmetic product	Main "green ingredients"	Type of product	Product claims	Reference
Rose Oil Nourishing Treatment	Apricot kernel oil; squalane; rosehip seed oil; <i>Rosa damascena</i> flower extract	Face oil	Nourishing and antioxidant properties; helps diminish the look of fine lines and wrinkles	https://heritagestore.com
Shampoo Sweet Sensation	Apricot kernel oil	Shampoo	Moisturizing, soothing, and cleansing properties	https://benecos.uk/
Eye Makeup Remover	Apricot kernel oil; rice oil; jojoba oil; castor oil	Eye makeup remover	Cleansing properties; eyelash-boosting and growth-enhancing activity	https://youandoil.it/
Apricot Day Cream	Apricot kernel oil; avocado oil; fermented cereal extract; jojoba oil; St. John's wort; sweet almond oil	Face cream	Nourishing and revitalizing properties; activates the skin's own oil-moisture balance; strengthens resilience	https://www.drhauschka.de
Fair Squared Apricot Lip Balm	Apricot kernel oil; almond oil; lime extract; shea butter	Lip balm	Protecting and nourishing dry, chapped lips	https://www.fairsquared.com/

characterized by good spreadability and permeability due to the presence of oleic acid and its well-known penetration-enhancing properties.

Its therapeutic application has been examined in several studies. Li et al. (2025) investigated its anti-inflammatory and anti-seborrheic properties in a dinitrofluorobenzene-induced rat model. According to the results, apricot kernel oil successfully inhibited several inflammatory cytokines (interleukin-6, interleukin-1 β , interleukin-10, and tumor necrosis factor- α) and proteins associated with seborrheic dermatitis, such as matrix metalloproteinases 2 and 9. The histopathological studies performed revealed the restorative effects of apricot kernel oil on skin integrity (Li et al. 2025).

Another beneficial effect of topical application is reported in the study by Gebreel et al. (2019). Apricot seeds, along with curcumin, were shown to exhibit wound-healing properties when tested on a rat model with a second-degree burn wound. The biochemical and histopathological studies revealed that the tested mixture significantly decreased the size of the wound and inhibited the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines compared with the control group (Gebreel et al. 2019).

In their study, Hamid et al. (2024) investigated the antimicrobial potential of bitter apricot kernel oil on various strains of microorganisms. The highest antimicrobial activity was observed against *S. aureus* and

Conclusion

Vegetable oils are typically extracted from plant seeds or kernels using the cold-pressing technique, which preserves all valuable ingredients. They possess various advantageous characteristics when topically applied, such as antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity, emollient and nourishing properties, as well as photoprotective and wound-healing efficacy, which are attributed to their diverse constituents (fatty acids, phenolic compounds, phytosterols, and other bioactive molecules). Their lipophilic nature further facilitates permeation through the skin, resulting in improved cosmetic or therapeutic efficacy. The comparative analysis in this review outlines the characteristic properties of the reviewed oils, including the pronounced wound-healing and antioxidant effects of rosehip oil, the emollient and barrier-restoring properties of apricot kernel oil, and the emerging skin-firming and antioxidant potential of Japanese quince oil.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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